

EarlyCause

Causative mechanisms & integrative models linking early-life-stress to psycho-cardio-metabolic multi-morbidity

Deliverable D1.2

Project website and communication materials

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Lead Beneficiary	Universitat de Barcelona (UB)
Author(s)	Katharina Heil, Karim Lekadir
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20/05/2020	V2	Katharina Heil	Update content – especially website screenshots and material information
26/05/2020	V3	Karim Lekadir	Review and updates
28/05/2020	V4	Katharina Heil	Updated final screenshots
29/05/2020	Final	Katharina Heil & Karim Lekadir	Final, approved version

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the process of design, collective refinement and implementation of the EarlyCause project's public website and communication material.

The report offers a comprehensive overview of how the logo was designed, website has been structured and how other communication material was designed.

The website design process has been led by Universitat de Barcelona (UB) with support of subcontractor, EuropeScience, the Project Coordinator (PC) and Project Manager (PM). It is based on an interactive layout, where visitors will become a comprehensive general view of the project rationale and mission, workplan and implementation, consortium partners with respective roles, as well as details of the project. Most importantly, though, it will represent the engagement and communication platform to share EarlyCause project advances, share publications and results as well as speak to the public and attract possible collaborators all of which are key objectives of the project.

It will also serve as a point of reference for anyone interested in following the day-to-day life and progress of the project - timely showcasing project events and presentations, publications, achievements and other updates – and allows to get in touch with the consortium. The website will also report all the produced dissemination material and make it available by linking to an external EarlyCause-dedicated collection (“community”) created ad hoc in Zenodo, the open-access repository developed in the context of the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN.

The implementation roadmap and the final outlook with up-to-date screenshots and infographics are presented. The release of the website is planned for June 15th 2020.

The EarlyCause website can be found at: www.earlycause.eu/.

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2 Project branding

For EarlyCause to develop its own (visual) identity a crucial step was to develop the project logo. Its use by all partners will ensure recognition of the project during its active time and beyond.

The following sections briefly describe the development and underlying explanations of how the logo was put together and reflects the projects identity.

2.1 Project logo

The conception of the logo underwent multiple phases, including design of a few visual concepts, selection and re-elaboration of some of them. The final version was agreed upon after consultation with WP leaders and the consortium.

The final logo can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: The EarlyCause logo.

The logo emblem includes a heart and brain, two central organs, part of the project. They visualize the link between Early Life Stress (ELS), depression and cardiovascular diseases.

The colour combination is positive, reflecting the intention of the EarlyCause project to use its research to identify ELS links to multi-morbidity always focusing on how to use the new knowledge to help people affected.

The logo has been elaborated in all its versions (coloured, black, white; see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Black and white version of the EarlyCause logo.

The font used in the logo is: Roboto Condense. This can be substituted in other materials and depending on the software used with the following alternatives, in the given (descending) order: Helvetica Neue, Helvetica, Arial, sans-serif. This will ensure an overall nice and comprehensive appearance.

2.2 Project Colours

Based on the red and blue used in the EarlyCause logo two lighter red and blue tones were defined. Figure 2 shows the colours and gives specifications.

Figure 3: EarlyCause colours (logo and light version).

More details on the visual project identity will be shared as a style guide with the consortium, integrated to Deliverable D1.3 “Quality Assurance Guidelines”.

3 EarlyCause website

The EarlyCause website can be found under: www.earlycause.eu.

Apart from giving EarlyCause its visual identity the logo also sets the baseline to develop EarlyCause’s website and communication material.

The following sections describe the website and its development in more detail.

Website design started in M2 and has been finalised in M4. Once the structure was defined the implementation started, undergoing several iterative cycles.

The creation and review process began with a preliminary conception of structure and production of relevant contents by UB. A first version of the website was circulated amongst WP leaders for feedback and input, leading to the final version as presented below. With further progress of the project additional aspects can be added to the page layout

3.1 General considerations

As described in the project proposal, the EarlyCause website aims to be the central communication & dissemination space for the project. It presents the project to other researchers as well as the general public and allows everyone to engage. Most recent updates, findings and advances will be shared via the website as well.

Given these aims, the design and contents has followed a series of general, commonly agreed rules:

- Making the website *as interactive as possible* in order to favour a high level of engagement with users; ensuring frequent updates including news and events, publications and other produced materials, and much more;
- Maintaining a *high-level comprehensible language*, so to make project description and contents available for all types of audiences, including general public; similarly, all project description will be elaborated starting from the proposal relevant sections but highly summarised, making these readable and concise.

3.2 Structure

The website has been structured in a modern layout based on one landing page with few subsection tabs (i.e., the home page and other 6 menu sections) readable by simple page scrolling, without the need of numerous clicks by the user. Page subsections are also directly accessible via a horizontal submenu at the top of each section, allowing to directly “jump” from one subsection to another by clicking on the relevant entries. The general structure and relevant contents are illustrated in Table 1)

Table 1: General website structure.

Sections	Subsections	Contents
Home/ Landing Page	-	<p><i>Top part (all visible without scrolling, on all pages)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Menu <p><i>Following parts (visible by scrolling down)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Description; • Summary news overview; • Most recent Publications; • Contact information. <p><i>Footer (at bottom of the page, visible on all pages):</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Funding banner • Share project – link to twitter
For Researchers	ELS	Introduction to Early Life Stress
	Research	Description of aims & objectives
	Methods	Overview of used methods
	Work Packages	WP overview – pop up option for further details
For the Public	What is ELS	ELS introduction
	Why does it matter?	Rational for/of the project
	What is EarlyCause investigating about ELS	Project explanation, covering objectives, expected outcome and findings.
	What is the expected impact?	Description of the impact the project findings can have on society.
Partners	Partner overview	Description of the consortium partner institutions (including logo, short description and link to website), list of team members per partner, with short descriptions and link to twitter/LinkedIn
	Partner Teams	
News	-	Project news overview (meetings, publications, other) and dissemination events (conferences, workshops, etc.).
Publications	-	Overview of publications.
Contact	-	Contact information of Project Coordinator and Project Manager.

4 Preview

This series of preview images illustrates the actual look of the website as it is being designed, based on the general structure detailed in the previous chapter. Please note that some of the texts are still under revision and might also be updated.

Based on the presented approach and defined elements and contents, we are now implementing the final structure and refining the relevant texts. As previously mentioned, the website is expected to go-

live on June 15th, 2020. We will then start its promotion via our social media channels and connect with other projects for a maximised outreach.

4.1 Home page

EARLY CAUSE

For Researchers For the Public Partners News Publications Contact

Investigating the lifelong effects of early life stress on health

Stress experienced in early stages of life – or possibly even during pregnancy is affecting 75% of pregnant women (and the unborn baby) – and nearly 50% of young children is

Investigating the lifelong effects of early life stress on health

Stress experienced in the early stages of life – from pregnancy to adolescence – is common and pervasive, affecting up to 75% of pregnant women (and the unborn baby) and nearly 50% of children, with long term consequences for development and health. The EarlyCause project will study the hypothesis that early life stress (ELS), a well-established risk factor for depressive, cardiovascular and metabolic disorders individually, is a cause of multi-morbidity in these disorders.

News

- Press Release**
1st official EarlyCause Announcement published
[Read more](#)
- Kick-off Meeting**
January 15th & 16th, Barcelona, Universitat de Barcelona
[Read more](#)

Publications

Cordis info
Understanding causative mechanisms in co- and multi-morbidities combining mental and nonmental disorders
[Read more](#)

Contact

EarlyCause Project Coordinator KATH LEHNER UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA kath.lehner@ub.edu	EarlyCause Project Manager CATERINA FERRI UNIVERSITAT DE BARCELONA caterina.ferrigub.edu
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Figure 4: Preview of the EarlyCause website home page.

4.2 Project

ELS

It has been shown that ELS can have long-lasting consequences on human health, and impact psychological and physiological processes level later in life. Some of the diseases which are most frequently linked with stress experiences in early life are depression, cardiovascular diseases and metabolic disorders, such as diabetes. Unfortunately these three diseases are often appearing together in the same patient – and one refers this as a multi-morbidity of these diseases.

Research

To better understand the links between ELS and depression, cardiovascular diseases and metabolic disorders, the EarlyCause project tries to find mechanisms that might be linking these diseases on a molecular/biological level. Therefore the project studies biological mechanisms, but also considers lifestyle and behavioural factors. Once (potential) causes have been identified protective mechanisms, so called "intervention strategies" will be studied and proposed to actively prevent the disease outbreak. Alternatively strategies to reverse causative mechanisms will be explored to reduce the effect of ELS in individuals at high risk of developing such multi-morbidities.

Methods

The EarlyCause project will use big data, animal experiments and artificial intelligence to identify new clinical knowledge, quantitative biomarkers and clinical tools to assess disease and comorbidity induced by early life stress. The highly multi-disciplinary and experienced consortium combines state-of-the-art and novel approaches from basic, pre-clinical and clinical research, including causal inference methods such as Mendelian randomisation, animal models of prenatal and postnatal stress, cellular models in various tissues, and integrative bioinformatics and machine learning methods.

Figure 6: For Researchers, scientific project description.

Workpackages

WP1 (UB, Katharina Heil) Coordination, dissemination and communication	WP2 (EMBL, Guy Cochrane) Centralised data coordination	WP3 (EMC, Charlotte Cecil/Janine Felix) Correlational studies
WP4 (OULU, Sylvain Sebert) Causal inference	WP5 (UZH, Isabelle Mansuy) Animal models	WP6 (KCL, Carmin Pariente & Alessa Borsini) Cellular models
WP7 (UB, Karim Lekadir) Integrated Models and Computational Tools	WP8 (EMP, Rainer Thiel) Impact Evaluation and Exploitation Planning	WP9 (UB, Karim L... Ethics work package

WP1 (UB, Katharina Heil)

Coordination, dissemination and communication

1. Financial aspects (via the Fundación Bosch i Gimpera, third party of the Universitat de Barcelona)
2. Deliverables, reporting and technical aspects (via Project Manager, Katharina Heil)
3. Overall project management

- Including meetings, progress, risk assessment

Figure 5: Overview of the EarlyCause Work Packages (WPs) and an example pop-up with further information (WP1).

4.3 For the Public

The EarlyCause Project

What is ELS?

Early life stress (ELS) is the experience of stressful or adverse conditions during a child's development, beginning anywhere from pregnancy to adolescence. When prenatal, ELS may be experienced because of maternal stress during pregnancy, while after birth, it can result from adverse events such as child abuse (sexual, physical, emotional) and neglect (emotional, physical), parental loss (death, separation), disease, accidents, exposure to war or terrorism-related events and/or natural disasters.

Why does it matter?

ELS matters because it can have a long-lasting impact on a child's development, health and wellbeing. For example, ELS can affect a child's neurodevelopment increasing the risk of cognitive, emotional and behavioural problems. In addition, ELS can dysregulate important physiological functions affecting the way a child may respond to future stressors. Importantly, ELS is a key determinant of health, not just early in life, but across the lifespan. It is known to dramatically increase the risk to develop a mental or physical illness and has been repeatedly associated with depression, anxiety, personality disorder but also cardiovascular, metabolic and autoimmune diseases, and possibly cancer. However, the biological mechanisms through which ELS affects health remain unclear.

What is EarlyCause investigating about ELS?

EarlyCause is investigating how ELS causes diseases in adulthood. Its approach is original and novel because it examines which aspects of ELS are linked to the concomitant development of psychological, cardiovascular and metabolic diseases together, a phenomenon called co-morbidity, which is responsible for the increased mortality linked to ELS. Further, EarlyCause assesses whether these co-morbid symptoms can be diminished or prevented by intervention to avoid disease. EarlyCause combines studies in large cohorts of humans across Europe and in validated cellular and animal models to identify the chain of molecular and biological events that are activated in the brain and body by ELS and result in clinical symptoms.

What is the expected impact?

The expected impact is to reveal how ELS results in mental and physical disorders, and how its effects can be prevented. It will identify new biological markers and facilitate the diagnostic of ELS diseases as well as the development of novel treatment strategies. EarlyCause is expected to help improve health and welfare of vulnerable individuals for a better world.

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Figure 7: For the Public page. Explaining the EarlyCause project to the general public.

4.4 Partners

Figure 8: Overview of the EarlyCause project partners (split over two pages).

4.5 News

Figure 9: News page with two first examples - as seen on landing/home page. Later on, this will be the news archive, with most recent news on the landing/home page only.

4.6 Publications

This part will be populated once first publications are under way and/or being published.

Publications

Cordis info

Understanding causative mechanisms in co- and multimorbidities combining mental and non-mental disorders

[Download PDF](#)

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Figure 10: Example entry on the Publications page.

4.7 Contact

Contact

For more information on the project you can contact our Project Coordinator or Project Manager:

EarlyCause Project Coordinator
Karim Lekadir
Universidad de Barcelona
karim.lekadir@ub.edu

EarlyCause Project Manager
Katharina Heil
Universidad de Barcelona
katharina.f.heil@ub.edu

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Figure 11: EarlyCause Project Coordinator and Project Manager contact details.

5 Visual Material

A number of visual materials have been produced and shared with Consortium partners to ensure a consistent project appearance, internally as well as towards external stakeholders.

This approach is in line with the established communication and dissemination (C&D) purposes.

5.1 Banners for acknowledgment of funding

A banner for acknowledgement of funding from the European Union (EU), necessary for the website as well as all the other C&D materials, was created. The banner have been designed based on the format indicated on the European Commission website, in the *Acknowledgement of EU funding* section of the *Participant Portal Horizon 2020 Online Manual*¹, also taking into account the manual “*The use of the EU emblem in the context of EU programmes*”². The phrase has been defined based on the standard formula indicated in the EC manual.

The banner has been produced in two A4-based versions, as a colour and blue-white version (see Figure 9). Additional formats can be generated as required (e.g. as seen on the pptx slides further below).

The digital version as well as a modifiable pptx file can be found [here](#).

Figure 12: Banner for acknowledgment of funding.

5.2 Presentation templates

To achieve a unique public presence, EarlyCause members are encouraged to use the projects presentation template, which can be downloaded in pptx format from the shared folder ([here](#)).

The design coincides with graphical elements and colours used in the logo, making the project branding consistent. Figure 13 shows the five available templates – these can be adapted by all consortium partners as required, depending on the occasion and use.

¹ [Grant Management, Acknowledge Funding](#), retrieved on 21/05/2020

² [EU emblem use guidelines](#), retrieved on 21/05/2020

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Place
Date
Name, Surname, affiliation

Thank you!

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@EarlyCause

20/05/2020 3 20/05/2020 4

The Consortium

Figure 13: EarlyCause power point templates.

5.3 Online Presence

An EarlyCause twitter account was set up at the start of the project:

@EarlyCause; <https://twitter.com/EarlyCause>.

The header can be seen in Figure 11. It shows the EarlyCause logo as well as a picture of many consortium members, during the kick-off meeting, held at University of Barcelona in January 2020.

Figure 14: EarlyCause's twitter header.

The twitter channel which already counts with a number of followers will be used for dissemination & communication (C&D) purposes, allowing to spread news items, updates, research outcomes and others quickly across consortium members and with their, as well as other project networks.

6 Summary

The presented deliverable presents the EarlyCause website layout as well as other communication materials.

It sets the baseline for the projects (visual) identity, allowing all consortium members to align with it, ensuring a cohesive image and generating recognisability.

The website can be found at: www.earlycause.eu and the official launch is planned for June 15th 2020